

Multi-scale Thermal Uniformity Optimization in Methane-Fueled Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFCs)

Chang'an Dublin International College of Transportation

Group-5

Weihao Chen¹, Yixin Gao¹, Ziqiao Zhou¹, Shengyao Wang¹

¹ Chang'an Dublin International College of Transportation, Chang'an University, Xi'an, Shaanxi Province, China

Academic Course Module: Thermodynamics 2 (MEEN2007W) & Mechanics of Fluids 2 (MEEN3005W)

Contact Email: chenweihao637@163.com; Course Instructors: Muhammad Sajid, Xuehui Wang, Pei Fu

Weihao Chen
23219291

Yixin Gao
23219352

Shengyao Wang
23219325

Ziqiao Zhou
23219342

Introduction

What are Methane-Direct Solid Oxide Fuel Cells?

It is a type of solid oxide fuel cells that converts methane directly to electricity via internal reforming, without external reformers [2].

Why is thermal uniformity optimization important?

It prevents thermal stress and material degradation caused by thermodynamic mismatch, ensuring long-term durability for Methane-Direct SOFCs [1].

What metrics are used to evaluate Thermal Uniformity?

Methodology Flow Chart

Recent Studies on Thermal Uniformity Improvement

Simulation Result & Thermal Uniformity Analysis

Micro Structure Level

Single Cell Level

Figure 9. Temperature Distribution in Different Flow Channels (L_x & L_w)

Cells System Level

Cooling Method	Cooling Medium	$\Delta T / (\frac{\partial T}{\partial L})_{before}$	$\Delta T / (\frac{\partial T}{\partial L})_{after}$
Excess air cooling	Air	21 K cm ⁻¹	14 K cm ⁻¹
Independent gas cooling	Argon (Ar) and air	88.36 K	45.31 K
Liquid cooling	Pressurized water cooling (Planar stack)	185 K	26 K
	Pressurized water cooling (Tubular stack)	295 K	62 K
	Liquid tin (Sn)	60 K	15 K
Heat pipe cooling	Na (Planar stack)	43 K	15 K
	Na (Tubular cell)	31 K cm ⁻¹	13 K cm ⁻¹
	Not specified	111 K	25 K

System-level thermal management, particularly liquid cooling, can significantly suppress the stack-level temperature gradients and maximum ΔT induced by direct internal reforming (DIR) [4].

Conclusions

- Anode Porosity:** Improvement from the Micro-level → Highly parameter-sensitive. Case 1 shows the best thermal uniformity, with the lowest $\Delta T = 4.2$ K.
- Flow-channel:** Transport enhanced → Performance vs. ΔT trade-off. Trapezoidal and bow-shaped improve current density by 15-16%, but increase local ΔT by nearly 7 K, and optimized trapezoidal channel can reduce temperature gradient by 24%.
- System cooling:** External complement → Achieves overall improvement. Liquid cooling significantly reduces stack thermal gradients, lowering ΔT to 26 K.

Trade-off & Future Work

- Methane-specific Focus:** While existing literature predominantly addresses general SOFCs, dedicated thermal management mechanisms tailored for methane-fueled SOFCs are urgently required.
- Cross-scale Synergy:** Transitioning from single-scale studies to deeply coupling anode porosity, flow-channel architecture, and system-level thermal management.
- Comprehensive Evaluation:** Expanding beyond the sole metric of thermal uniformity to comprehensively incorporate long-term durability and manufacturing cost assessments.

REFERENCE LIST:

[1] Direct methane fuel Cells: Developments, challenges, and prospects, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.237707>

[2] Optimization Study on Performance of Automotive Anode-Supported Solid Oxide Fuel Cells with Gradient Components Anode, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42154-025-00399-z>

[3] Effects of bipolar plate flow channel configuration on thermal-electric performance of direct ammonia solid oxide fuel cell: Part I- Numerical study of channel section geometry, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydene.2023.09.028>

[4] Thermal gradient management in solid oxide fuel cells: Mechanisms, strategies, and future directions, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.238017>

[5] Analysis on temperature uniformity in methane-rich internal reforming solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs), 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydene.2024.01.071>

[6] Investigation of creep damage and failure probability in solid oxide fuel cells with different flow channel geometries, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydene.2024.07.232>

SCAN THE QR CODE TO READ MORE...

